

ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS OF POLYFOCAL PUNCTION BIOPSY PROSTATE GLAND

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Annotation: This article analyzes the results of a polyfocal puncture prostate biopsy in 537 patients, 380 of them were diagnosed with prostate cancer glands (PCa). In the group of patients with diagnosed prostate cancer, older men prevailed age group, the average age of which was 71 ± 10 years (41–91 years). Methods examinations in our work were: determination of the level of common specific antigen prostate gland (PSA). As clarifying research methods, we used polyfocal puncture biopsy of the prostate gland with histological examination material, using Gleason scores to assess histological verification of the pathological process.

Key words: prostate cancer, prostate specific antigen (PSA), polyfocal puncture biopsy, Gleason score.

One of the most important problems of preserving male health is prostate cancer (PCa), which affects 679,000 men and causes every year 221,000 deaths. In the etiopathogenesis of prostate cancer gland the following factors play an important role:

- constitutional risk factors (obesity increases risk),
- age-related (at least 0.7% are diagnosed under 50 years of age) of these neoplasms, and after the age of 65 years, 75–85% of cases are diagnosed),
- ethnic, racial, geographical (currently time the highest incidence rates were identified in African Americans, and the lowest in Southeast Asia),
- genetic and family factors (13–26% of all cases prostate cancer, of which 5% have autosomal dominant inheritance).

As an early diagnosis of prostate cancer and monitoring the development of this disease in the late 80s. began to define prostate specific antigen (PSA) level in blood serum using immunoenzyme and radioimmunoassays. Will efficiency improve? Treatment after PSA screening in older men 50 years? Until recently, this test was golden standard in conducting examinations in men for subject of prostate cancer detection. However,

United States Targeted Prevention Service (The U.S. Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF) does not recommend conducting a PSA test for the screening diagnosis of prostate cancer in men over 50 years of age, justifying this fact by the fact that the PSA test does not provide an accurate answer to the question of what kind of cancer the patient has (aggressive or non-aggressive), which can subsequently lead to unnecessary surgical and radiation treatment accompanied by a large amount complications [1].

According to the European Association of Urology determination of PSA level in blood serum as a Screening diagnosis of prostate cancer leads to overdiagnosis of the latter. In addition, in 15–20% of cases of prostate cancer determined in men with PSA levels within the reference values [2, 3].

Therefore, according to the clinical recommendations of the Association of Oncologists of Russia, there is no specific discriminatory PSA level, a single determination of this indicator is uninformative, and therefore PSA levels should be monitored over time [4]. Because a single determination of total PSA is uninformative, The European Association of Urology recommends determining the free PSA/total PSA ratio for reliability of the obtained analysis result at a total PSA value of 10 ng. With the fPSA/tPSA ratio less than 15% – the prognosis is unfavorable, which makes it possible to suspect prostate cancer.

PSA screening has been shown to reduce mortality from cancer, but at the same time it can cause overdiagnosis, thereby provoking serious complications, caused by the treatment of early forms and due to the fact that that oncology uses aggressive

treatment methods (extended surgical interventions, radiation therapy, chemotherapy, hormone therapy), which can significantly affect the patient's quality of life.

Purpose of the study: to identify the relationship between the degree of malignancy of prostate cancer and the level of PSA in the blood.

Material and methods

In the urology and oncology departments performed a polyfocal puncture biopsy of the prostate gland from 12 points (to obtain enough material for the study) in 537 patients, in 380 of them it was detected prostate cancer.

Histological assessment of prostate cancer differentiation was carried out in biopsy centers. To evaluate histological verification of the pathological process was used Gleason score according to the grading scale Gleason.

The received data was processed in programs Microsoft Excel and Statistica 6 using descriptive statistics methods (number of observations, mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values).

Results and its discussion

The age of the examined patients with prostate diseases varied from 41 to 91 years. In Group patients with diagnosed prostate cancer average age was 71 ± 10 years (41–91 years), with detected benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) age was 69 ± 9 years (48–91 years). Age heterogeneity in the distribution of patients by nosology was not observed: both PCa and BPH were determined mainly in older age group. Average PSA level in the group patients with diagnosed prostate cancer was 22.3 ± 2.25 ng/ml (max: 842 ng/ml, min: 0.2 ng/ml), in the group of patients with BPH 9.15 ± 0.65 ng/ml (min: 0.3 ng/ml, max: 68.3 ng/ml).

The blood PSA level in patients with diagnosed prostate cancer exceeds the same indicator in those studied with BPH. In some patients, a slight increase in PSA levels was detected in benign hyperplasia, PSA values fluctuate in prostate cancer from high (842 ng/ml) to normal levels.

The value of the threshold level of PSA in blood serum in screening programs is focused on 4 ng/ml. In the table data on serum PSA levels in patients are presented with prostate cancer and BPH.

In most prostate cancer patients the concentration PSA in blood serum fluctuated within the range: up to 4 ng/ml and 4–10 ng/ml – in 68 (17.9%) and 105 (27.6%) patients, respectively, 10–20 ng/ml – 108 patients (28.4%), 20–50 ng/ml — in 74 patients (19.5%), 50–100 ng/ml - in 16 (4.2%) patients and above 100 ng/ml was in 9 (2.4%) patients. Study J. Oesterling showed that 20–40% of all malignant prostate tumors are accompanied by normal serum PSA concentration.

Similar results were obtained in this work: in 17.9–27.6% normal PSA concentrations are observed.

According to J. Oesterling, the sensitivity of the method is insufficient to detect latent, focal, well-differentiated prostate cancer, so it is proposed assess the differentiation of prostate cancer in biopunctures using the Gleason score. The following data was received:

- in 77 cases a very aggressive low-grade form of cancer was found (8–10 points);
- in 52 cases – a highly differentiated form of cancer with a very low degree of aggression (2–4 points);
- in 251 cases – a moderately aggressive form of cancer (5–7 points).

When analyzing the dependence of the degree of malignancy PCa and blood PSA level correlation coefficient moments of products (Pearson coefficient) was 0.107, which indicates a significant positive correlation. Positive Pearson coefficient allows us to talk about the existence of a correlation dependence of blood PSA level on the degree of malignancy of prostate cancer.

TABLE. Serum PSA level (ng/ml)

Age	Average serum PSA level (ng/ml)		
	normal	prostate cancer	BPH
40-49	2.5	5.6	5.9
50-59	3.5	21.3	10.2
60-69	4.5	27.8	8.5
More than 70	6.5	20.2	9,5

Conclusions

Thus, the resulting directly proportional dependence suggests that the higher the level total PSA in the blood serum of patients, the more aggressive the form of cancer according to the results of histological assessment in biopunctures using Gleason scores. However, the results of the study showed that 17.9–27.6% of all malignant neoplasms of the prostate gland are accompanied by PSA concentrations in blood serum within reference values. Moreover, in the study conducted, both PCa and BPH was diagnosed mainly in the older age group.

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